

An Overview of Omentin-1

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ABSTRACT

Omentin-1, a recently identified 34 kDa secretory protein composed of 313 amino acids, is also known as intelectin-1. This adipokine is primarily synthesized in the stromal-vascular cells of visceral adipose tissue, particularly in omental and epicardial fat, but is also present in various other organs and tissues. Omentin-1, encoded by the ITLN-1 gene, is recognized as the predominant circulating form. Its folding and maturation occur in the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus; although its specific receptor has not yet been identified, omentin-1 influences multiple signaling pathways, including AMPK, Akt, eNOS, PPAR- δ , JAK2/STAT3, and PI3K/Akt. It exhibits anti-inflammatory, anti-atherosclerotic, cardioprotective, antioxidant, insulin-sensitizing, and bone-protective biological activities. Clinically, plasma omentin-1 levels have been reported to be significantly reduced in conditions such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, polycystic ovary syndrome, metabolic syndrome, and certain cardiovascular diseases. Omentin-1 levels are inversely correlated with insulin resistance and body fat accumulation. In the cardiovascular system, it exerts protective effects by preventing vascular calcification, supporting vasodilation, and facilitating collateral vessel development. In osteoarthritis, it reduces cartilage degradation and helps maintain joint health. Its relationship with cancer is complex, with elevated levels observed in some gastrointestinal tumors and reduced levels in breast and ovarian cancers. The aim of this review is to provide a general overview of omentin-1, describe its biological functions, and summarize the current literature on its associations with various diseases.

Keywords: Adipokine, Omentin, Systemic diseases

Omentin-1 Üzerine Genel Bir Bakış

ÖZ

Omentin-1, yakın zamanda tanımlanmış, 34 kDa ağırlığında ve 313 amino asitten oluşan bir salgı proteinidir. İntelektin-1 olarak da bilinen bu adipokin, başlıca visseral yağ dokusunun (özellikle omental ve epikardiyal) stromal-vasküler hücrelerinde sentezlenmekle birlikte, çeşitli organ ve dokularda da bulunur. ITLN-1 geni tarafından kodlanan omentin-1'in dolaşımdaki baskın form olduğu bilinmektedir. Katlanma ve olgunlaşma süreçleri endoplazmik retikulum ve Golgi aygıtında gerçekleşir; spesifik reseptörü henüz tanımlanmamış olmakla birlikte AMPK, Akt, eNOS, PPAR- δ , JAK2/STAT3 ve PI3K/Akt gibi birçok sinyal yolunu etkiler. Anti-inflamatuar, anti-aterosklerotik, kardiyoprotektif, antioksidan, insülin duyarlılığını artırıcı ve kemik koruyucu biyolojik aktivitelere sahiptir. Klinik olarak, obezite, tip 2 diyabet, polikistik over sendromu, metabolik sendrom ve bazı kardiyovasküler hastalıklar gibi durumlarda plazma omentin-1 seviyelerinin belirgin şekilde azaldığı gösterilmiştir. Omentin-1 düzeyleri, insülin direnci ve vücut yağlanması ile ters orantılıdır. Kardiyovasküler sistemde damar kalsifikasyonunu önleyici, vazodilatasyonu destekleyici ve kollateral damar gelişimini kolaylaştırıcı etkiler gösterir. Osteoartritte kırıldık yıkımını azaltarak eklem sağlığını korur. Onkoloji alanında ise farklı kanser türleriyle ilişkisi kompleks olup, bazı gastrointestinal tümörlerde yüksek, meme ve over kanserinde düşük seviyeler bildirilmiştir. Bu derlemenin amacı, Omentin-1 hakkında genel bilgi sunmak, biyolojik fonksiyonlarını açıklamak ve hastalıklarla olan ilişkisini ortaya koyarak mevcut literatürü özetlemektir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Adipokin, Omentin, Sistemik hastalıklar

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1. INTRODUCTION

Recently identified omentin-1 (omentin) is a 34 kDa adipose tissue-specific secretory protein composed of 313 amino acids [1]. It is also referred to as intelectin-1, galactofuranose-binding lectin, or intestinal lactoferrin receptor. This adipocytokine is predominantly synthesized in the stromal-vascular cells of visceral adipose tissue—particularly omental and epicardial fat—rather than subcutaneous adipose depots [2]. In addition, it has been detected in mesothelial cells, vascular structures, goblet cells, the small intestine and colon, ovaries, placenta, and blood plasma [3,4]. Expression in tissues such as the heart and lungs has also been reported, suggesting a variety of physiological functions [1,5]. Omentin-1 is encoded by the ITLN-1 gene located on chromosome region 1q22–q23, which has been associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus [6]. Due to its homotrimeric structure, omentin-1 exhibits bone loss-preventive [7], insulin-sensitizing [8], and anti-inflammatory properties [9]. Furthermore, it has been reported to exert anti-inflammatory, anti-atherosclerotic, cardioprotective, and antioxidant effects [10].

The biosynthesis and biological activities of the polypeptides constituting omentin depend on the presence of specific amino acid residues, such as cysteine, lysine, and serine. These residues facilitate the formation of disulfide bonds, cross-linking, and various post-translational modifications. The amino acid sequence, synthesized on ribosomes according to the genetic code, determines the primary structure of the polypeptides. This primary structure plays a crucial role in protein folding, stability, and biological activity. Omentin synthesis typically involves the cooperative action of multiple polypeptide chains. Most of the synthetic process occurs in the endoplasmic reticulum, where folding, disulfide bond formation, and quality control mechanisms are carried out. Subsequently, the protein is processed in the Golgi apparatus, packaged into secretory vesicles, and released into the extracellular space via exocytosis [1]. Although specific receptors for omentin have not yet been identified, it is known to exist in two isoforms, synthesized in the 1q22–q23 chromosomal region. Omentin-1 is one of these two isoforms—omentin-1 and omentin-2—which share approximately 83% amino acid sequence similarity [11], and it is recognized as the predominant circulating form [12].

Omentin expression is upregulated by various transcription factors and signaling pathways involved in adipogenesis, including Wnt/ β -catenin signaling, CCAAT/enhancer-binding proteins (C/EBPs), and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR- γ). Upon activation of these regulatory elements, preadipocytes differentiate into mature adipocytes, thereby enhancing the synthesis and secretion of omentin [12].

Omentin-1 activates the AMPK pathway and enhances endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) phosphorylation in vascular endothelial cells, leading to increased nitric oxide production and improved endothelial function. Additionally, in these cells, omentin-1 reduces TNF- α -induced pro-inflammatory responses and oxidative stress, demonstrating its anti-inflammatory and antioxidative effects [13]. However, omentin not only activates the AMPK pathway but also induces the

phosphorylation of other proteins such as Akt and eNOS. Furthermore, it has been shown to upregulate the expression of PPAR- δ [14]. In adipose tissue, omentin has been reported to suppress the pro-inflammatory TXNIP/NLRP3 pathway [15]. While enhancing the expression of mitochondrial biogenesis regulators such as PGC-1 α and NRF-1 [16,17], omentin reduces IRF-1 expression by inhibiting the JAK2/STAT3 pathway—a mechanism observed in chondroblasts [18]. Additionally, omentin has been reported to interact with several transcription factors linked to tumorigenesis, including EN1, NFIC, ELK4, GATA2, JUND, FOXA1, and YY1 [19]. In hepatocellular carcinoma, omentin contributes to the stabilization of p53 and p21 proteins, thereby modulating the JNK pathway, on tumor cells [20]. Conversely, in hepatic macrophages, omentin reduces mTOR pathway activation, providing a protective effect on liver health [21]. Regarding renal function, omentin has been found to decrease the expression of certain cytokines, such as TNF- α and IFN- γ , and to attenuate oxidative stress. This renoprotective action is thought to be associated with the downregulation of miR-27a gene expression in patients with type 2 diabetic nephropathy [22].

The aim of this review is to summarize the relationship between omentin-1 and various diseases, including metabolic disorders, cardiovascular diseases, osteoarthritis, and different types of tumors. Clinical and experimental studies reported in the current literature were evaluated to discuss how changes in omentin-1 levels may contribute to disease pathophysiology. This review also highlights the potential of omentin-1 as a diagnostic/prognostic biomarker and possible therapeutic target.

1.1. Metabolic Disorders

It has been reported that omentin-1 levels in visceral adipose tissue decrease in association with obesity. Moreover, reduced omentin concentrations have been observed in individuals with impaired glucose regulation, patients with type 1 or type 2 diabetes, as well as those with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and metabolic syndrome [23,24]. A common underlying feature of these conditions is insulin resistance and obesity, and omentin-1 expression has been described as inversely correlated with these metabolic disturbances [25]. Several studies further support that elevated omentin levels are associated with leanness or act as a protective factor against obesity [25,26,27].

According to data from a study in the literature, serum omentin-1 levels in patients with type 2 diabetes are significantly lower compared to controls. Consequently, in type 2 diabetes, the reduction in serum omentin-1 may contribute to insulin resistance by diminishing insulin-stimulated glucose uptake in insulin-sensitive tissues [28,29]. The relationship between omentin levels and type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) remains inconsistent across studies. While some reports have documented lower omentin concentrations in T1DM patients [30,31,32], another study has indicated higher levels [33]. Overall, omentin-1 is recognized as a regulatory adipokine in glucose metabolism, with potential roles in the

pathophysiology of insulin resistance. It exerts these effects primarily by enhancing insulin signaling through the activation of protein kinase B (Akt) and facilitating insulin-mediated glucose transport into adipocytes. Indeed, in one study, treatment with recombinant omentin-1 increased insulin-stimulated glucose uptake in both human subcutaneous and omental adipocytes, and also triggered Akt signaling activation in the presence or absence of insulin [34].

A negative correlation between body mass and plasma omentin concentrations has been reported in several studies, taking into account body mass index, plasma leptin concentration, and waist circumference-related adiposity [25,29]. However, the underlying mechanisms behind this relationship have not yet been clearly elucidated. It has been suggested that, particularly in obesity, this association may be linked to the elevated levels of certain pro-inflammatory mediators, such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-1 (IL-1) [7].

Numerous studies have reported that serum omentin-1 levels are significantly reduced in individuals with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) [28,35]. This reduction has been observed in parallel with insulin resistance, elevated TNF- α levels, and hyperandrogenism [35]. In a study by Cloix et al. (2014), omentin concentrations in the follicular fluid of PCOS patients were found to be higher than those in plasma [36].

Several studies have demonstrated that plasma omentin-1 levels are significantly reduced in individuals diagnosed with metabolic syndrome [25,28]. Notably, in patients with hypertension, low omentin-1 concentrations have been identified as an independent predictor of metabolic syndrome [37]. This reduction has also been associated with obesity and increased visceral adiposity, as visceral fat represents a primary source of omentin-1, and inflammation within this tissue may negatively influence adipokine levels [25].

1.2. Cardiovascular Disorders

Numerous studies have reported decreased omentin levels in individuals with carotid atherosclerosis and other cardiovascular diseases [38,39], coronary artery disease [40], heart failure [41], and dilated cardiomyopathy [42]. Additionally, omentin concentrations have been found to be reduced in patients with coronary artery disease and acute coronary syndrome [43]. Omentin has been shown to exert effects on the circulatory system, particularly providing a protective role against the calcification of vascular smooth muscle cells via the PI3K/Akt pathway. Additionally, it promotes vasodilation in arteries, an effect that is indirectly mediated through increased nitric oxide synthesis in endothelial cells [44].

In a study conducted on normotensive rats, administration of omentin-1 was shown to suppress agonist-induced increases in blood pressure, an effect believed to be mediated via nitric oxide-dependent mechanisms [45]. Another study suggested that omentin-1 levels could serve as a biomarker for prognostic assessment in patients with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy [46]. The inverse relationship between omentin-1 concentrations and obesity markers further indicates that omentin-1 may play a role in the progression of obesity-related cardiovascular diseases [47]. Moreover, plasma omentin-1 levels have been associated

with the development of advanced coronary collateral circulation, suggesting a potential role of omentin-1 in the formation of these vessels [48].

1.3. Osteoarthritis

Osteoarthritis, which arises as a consequence of chronic inflammation and can lead to permanent disability, is characterized by functional and structural deterioration of the joints and is frequently associated with obesity [49]. Recent studies have demonstrated a significant correlation between serum omentin-1 concentrations and the severity of osteoarthritis in obese individuals [50]. Exogenous administration of omentin has been shown to reduce the secretion of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) in cartilage tissue, prevent cartilage degradation, and slow the progression of osteoarthritis [18]. Additionally, omentin increases the production of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-4 in fibroblasts and reduces the synthesis of key pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α , which play a crucial role in OA pathogenesis [51,52]. Furthermore, omentin modulates macrophage behavior by shifting their phenotype toward the anti-inflammatory M2 type, which secretes higher levels of anti-inflammatory mediators, thereby exerting a potent osteoprotective effect [51].

1.4. Tumor

A correlation has been reported between elevated plasma omentin concentrations and the presence of gastrointestinal tumors [53,54]. Plasma omentin-1 levels in breast cancer patients have been reported as lower in some studies, while others found no significant differences, highlighting variability across cohorts [55,56]. Adipokine expression, including omentin-1, can be influenced by obesity and cachexia, making it challenging to delineate their specific roles in tumor biology [57]. Although omentin levels vary across different cancer types, its role in tumor progression and interactions with the immune system has not yet been fully elucidated [44]. In ovarian cancer, omentin expression is reduced in both surrounding tissues and throughout the organism [58]. Some studies suggest that omentin-1 may be altered in certain gastrointestinal tumors, although the results are variable and further research is needed [2,54]. Elevated levels have also been observed in prostate cancer [59].

Figure 1. Beneficial effects of Omentin-1 [60]

2.Future Perspectives

Growing evidence indicates that omentin-1 may serve as an important biomarker and potential therapeutic target for various systemic diseases. To fully establish its diagnostic and prognostic value—particularly in obesity, type 2 diabetes, and cardiovascular conditions—standardized measurement methods and large-scale clinical studies are essential. Therapeutic strategies aimed at increasing omentin-1 levels, including recombinant omentin-1 administration, could offer new ways to enhance insulin sensitivity, prevent vascular calcification, and protect cartilage in osteoarthritis. In the field of oncology, the complex and sometimes contradictory roles of omentin-1 warrant further investigation before clinical use can be considered. Future research should focus on clarifying these mechanisms and developing interventions that modulate omentin-1 levels to improve patient outcomes.

3.CONCLUSION

The effects of omentin-1 on various systemic diseases have increasingly attracted research interest. Its association with metabolic disorders, particularly obesity and type 2 diabetes, has long been recognized; through its insulin-sensitizing effects, omentin-1 may exert a protective role in these conditions. In the cardiovascular system, it has been shown to limit the development of atherosclerosis by inhibiting plaque formation within the vascular wall. Additionally, in cartilage tissue, omentin-1 suppresses the production of degradative enzymes, thereby slowing the progression of osteoarthritis. Regarding tumors, its effects are more complex; while it exhibits protective roles in certain cancer types, elevated omentin-1 levels have been linked to disease progression in gastrointestinal and prostate cancers. These conflicting findings may stem from omentin's bidirectional effects on the immune system and methodological differences across studies. Therefore, human-based, standardized research is needed to clarify the precise role of omentin in disease pathophysiology.

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